

Erratum to the article <Mushrooms adapted to seawater: two new species of *Candolleomyces* (Basidiomycota, Agaricales) from China>, and concerns on the taxonomic position of *Gautieria mianjin*

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Text

Dear colleagues,

In this letter, I would like to present the (1) erratum to my first-authored article <Mushrooms adapted to seawater: two new species of *Candolleomyces* (Basidiomycota, Agaricales) from China>, and (2) concerns on the taxonomic position of my first-authored taxon *Gautieria mianjin* Kun L. Yang, Xiao Liu & Zhu L. Yang (*Phytotaxa* 2023: 123).

(1) As the first author of this article published in *Journal of Fungi* (ISSN: 2309-608X) on December 16, 2023:

Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M. & Yang, Z.L. (2023). Mushrooms adapted to seawater: two new species of *Candolleomyces* (Basidiomycota, Agaricales) from China. *Journal of Fungi* 9 (12): 1204. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof9121204>

I should note the errors for its published version that have been noticed by myself so far:

Note 1. Page 6, in the legend of Figure 2: “from the laboratory culture L23267” should read “(c) from the laboratory culture L23267”, meaning that the (c) vegetative mycelium on seawater PDA in the illustration was observed from the laboratory culture L23267. During the editing process, “(c)” was mistakenly deleted.

Note 2. The paratypes “designated” in the section 3.4 Taxonomy and the “(PT)” marks in Figure 6 can be ignored, as according to the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code) Art. 9.7 “A paratype is any

specimen cited in the protologue that is neither the holotype nor an isotype, nor one of the syntypes if in the protologue two or more specimens were simultaneously designated as types”, thus actually the paratypes that we “designated” and the “Additional specimens examined” automatically became the paratypes. This issue was remind by the editor Eric McKenzie (Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research, New Zealand) in *Phytotaxa* while he was handling our *Pseudoplectania* paper. We really appreciate his kind guidance!

No errors have been reported by readers so far. If you notice any please contact me, thanks. Apologize for any inconvenience about the errors! I will keep improving my mycological skills.

(2) As the first author of the taxon *Gautieria mianjin* Kun L. Yang, Xiao Liu & Zhu L. Yang (*Phytotaxa* 2023: 123), I would like to update some timely notes concerning its taxonomic position.

On May 17, 2023, Hua Qu (Kunming Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China) reminded me that an article about European *Gautieria* was just published, viz. Vidal et al. (2023), and its molecular data suggest a close relationship between the “*Gautieria villosa*” and *G. xinjiangensis* (seems to be the sister taxon of *G. mianjin*, see Yang et al. (2023b); see also Figure 4), immediately caught my attention (Thanks for Qu’s reminder!).

As *G. villosa* was not accepted by Species Fungorum (<https://www.speciesfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp>; even today when I am writing this article it is still not accepted: Figure 1), I did not consider a comparison with this taxon when I proposed *G. mianjin*. However, Vidal et al. (2023) resurrected the name *G. villosa* after they examined the European specimens, with detailed morphological, ITS and nrLSU data. I was surprised that *G. villosa* was divided in three varieties with quite different basidiospore sizes as described by the authors, and that any one of them was also quite different from that of *G. mianjin*. Therefore, I believe that, even if I had traced the protologue of *G. villosa*, I still would not associate it with *G. mianjin*!

▲ Figure 1. Screenshot of the *Gautieria* search page in Species Fungorum

(<https://www.speciesfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp>) and Index Fungorum (<http://www.indexfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp>) on June 9, 2024. Referred to Wikipedia (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Index_Fungorum): "... the Index Fungorum results also give a cross-reference to Species Fungorum where an entry is available—names without such a reference are generally only of historical interest and should not be considered reliable for present use". Please check this figure on a magnifiable screen of electronic equipment.

▲ **Figure 2.** Distribution pattern of the basidiospore measurements (length, width, and length/width ratio (Q), (generally) including ornamentation) of *Gautieria villosa* (with three varieties), *G. mianjin* and *G. xinjiangensis*. Darker areas represent (generally) $\geq 90\%$ measured values (if mentioned in the original references), while lighter areas extending to the extreme values. Measurements of *G. villosa* referred to Vidal et al. (2023), *G. mianjin* to Yang et al. (2023b), and *G. xinjiangensis* to Bau & Liu (2013).

To further confirm the phylogenetic position of *G. mianjin*, with the assistance of Xiao Liu (Government Offices Administration of Lintan County, China), Jia Y. Lin (College of Plant Protection, South China Agricultural University, China) and Guang-Mei Li (Yunnan Key Laboratory for Fungal Diversity and Green Development, Kunming Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China), I got the second specimen of *G. mianjin* growing on the original collection site of the holotype on August 23, 2023 (Thanks for their kind help!). Its ITS and nrLSU sequences are 100% identical with those of the holotype ensuring the accuracy. The phylogenetic analysis with these sequences and specimens of clades "*GauGau-2*" and "*GauGau-3*" in Vidal et al. (2023) as ingroup, and a specimen of clade "*GauGau-1*" in Vidal et al. (2023) as outgroup (Table 1), using Maximum Likelihood method as described in Yang et al. (2023b), shows that the two current species *G. mianjin* and *G. xinjiangensis* and three varieties of *G. villosa* establishing a monophyletic group supported by 81% bootstrap (Figure 4), implying that the accurate positions of *G. mianjin* and *G. xinjiangensis* are not further elucidated.

According to the morphological examination, the basidiospores subglobose to broadly ellipsoid when mature still represent a significant characteristic for *G. mianjin*

(Figures 2 & 3), but the phylogeny seems disagreeing it to signal a independent species. A possible treatment may be downgrading *G. mianjin* as a variety of *G. villosa*. I am planning to deal with it in a study regarding false truffles from China in the near future.

▲ **Figure 3.** Morphology of *Gautieria mianjin*. (A1–A2) Immature basidiomata with preserved peridium (A1, photo by Xiao Liu) and mature basidiomata with practically absent peridium (A2, photo by Jia Y. Lin) (HTBM1288, the second collection made in this study). (B1–B2) Basidiospores under normal light microscope ($\approx 400\times$) (HTBM1288, the second collection made in this study, photos by Kun L. Yang). (C1–C2) Basidiospores under differential interference contrast microscope ($\approx 1000\times$) (HKAS126926, holotype, photos by Kun L. Yang; Thanks to Zhu L. Yang (Yunnan Key Laboratory for Fungal Diversity and Green Development, Kunming Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China) and Zhi-Jia Gu (Platform for Plant Multi-dimensional Imaging and Diversity Analysis, Kunming Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China) for their assistance in photographing!). (D1–D2) Basidiospores under scanning electron microscope ($\approx 4000\times$ (D1, shows immature oblong smooth ones and mature subglobose to broadly ellipsoid ornamented ones) & $\approx 20,000\times$ (D2, shows a section of spore wall)) (HKAS126926, holotype, photos by Kun L. Yang; Thanks to Zhi-Jia Gu for his assistance in photographing!).

▼ **Table 1.** Information of the specimens used in the phylogenetic analysis. The specimen sequenced in this study is in bold. The mark (HT) represents holotype.

Taxa	Voucher Nos.	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.	
			ITS	nrLSU
<i>G. convoluta</i> var. <i>convoluta</i>	TPN-19-0476	Poland	OL304005	OL304002
<i>G. convoluta</i> var. <i>convoluta</i>	ELG950600	Italy	OL304003	OL304004
<i>G. convoluta</i> var. <i>convoluta</i>	JMV20141014-27 (HT)	Spain	OL304007	OL304006
<i>G. convoluta</i> var. <i>petrakii</i>	M126216 (HT)	Czech Republic	OL304009	-
<i>G. mianjin</i>	HKAS126926 (HT)	China	NR187094	NG229098
<i>G. mianjin</i>	HTBM1288	China	PP542496	PP542495
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	KRAF-2012-152	Poland	OK669124	OK669120
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	HH2222Swiss	Switzerland	AF377066	-
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	JMV20090922-3	Spain	OK669122	-
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	UPSF-550626	Sweden	OK669117	-
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	M157765	Germany	OK998517	OK998518
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>inflata</i>	Ms1068	Italy	OK999968	-
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>inflata</i>	JMV20081021-5 (HT)	Spain	OK999965	-
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>inflata</i>	MA-Fungi5111	France	OK999967	-
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>inflata</i>	TPN-19-0123	Poland	OL036691	OL036693
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>pilifera</i>	JMV800561 (HT)	Greece	OL036694	OL036692
<i>G. villosa</i> var. <i>pilifera</i>	MG109	Greece	OL036695	OL036690
<i>G. xinjiangensis</i>	HMJAU6009 (HT)	China	NR153450	-
Outgroup				
<i>G. macrocoilia</i>	PRM678964	Czech Republic	OK669118	OK669119

ITS+nrLSU

0.004

▲ **Figure 4.** Phylogeny of *Gautieria mianjin* and related taxa inferred from the concatenated ITS-nrLSU dataset. Nodes are annotated if supported by $\geq 50\%$ bootstrap.

Three branches with distinct genetic distance are annotated with blue number. Specimen sequenced in this study is highlighted in bold. The mark (HT) represents holotype.

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Additional notes (if necessary)

Considering to post this article in memory of the last days of my 19 year old, now done (。í _ ì。)